

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

№ 2(11)

27.02.2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION

TADQIQ VA TATBIQ

ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

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Jurnal oyda bir
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Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
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DIAGNOSTICS AND NEW TREATMENT OPPORTUNITIES FOR PITUITARY ADENOMA

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Annotation. *Currently, the treatment of pituitary adenomas is inextricably linked with transsphenoidal neurosurgical intervention. Modern technologies used in surgery for this pituitary pathology, such as endoscopy using angular optics, as well as the use of specialized instruments, sealing and hemostatic materials, increase the effectiveness of surgical treatment of pituitary adenomas and reduce the incidence of intra- and postoperative complications. The development of radiation diagnostic methods, such as MRI, makes it possible to more accurately identify the formation of the pituitary gland, assess its size, direction of growth and the degree of invasion of surrounding tissues. The authors of the article described in detail the modern technique for endoscopic transsphenoidal removal of pituitary adenoma. Each stage of the operation is outlined step by step, taking into account various anatomical features and illustrated. This article also discusses the MR characteristics of pituitary adenomas: tumor size, direction of its growth, degree of invasion of the cavernous sinuses, compression effect on the structures of the chiasm-sellar region. The use of modern diagnostic and treatment methods significantly increases the effectiveness of neurosurgical intervention and reduces the risk of complications in patients.*

Key words: *pituitary adenoma; endoscopy; transsphenoidal approach; somatotropinoma; corticotropinoma.*

ДИАГНОСТИКА И НОВЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ АДЕНОМЫ ГИПОФИЗА

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Аннотация. *В настоящее время лечение аденом гипофиза неразрывно связано с трансфеноидальным нейрохирургическим вмешательством. Современные технологии, используемые в хирургии данной патологии гипофиза, такие как эндоскопия с использованием угловой оптики, а также*

использование специализированного инструментария, пломбирующих и гемостатических материалов, повышают эффективность хирургического лечения аденом гипофиза и снижают частоту интра- и послеоперационных осложнений. Развитие методов лучевой диагностики, таких как МРТ, позволяет более точно выявить образование гипофиза, оценить его размеры, направление роста и степень инвазии в окружающие ткани. Авторы статьи подробно описали современную технику эндоскопического трансфеноидального удаления аденомы гипофиза. Каждый этап операции пошагово расписан с учетом различных анатомических особенностей и проиллюстрирован. В статье также рассмотрены МР-характеристики аденом гипофиза: размеры опухоли, направление ее роста, степень инвазии кавернозных синусов, компрессионное влияние на структуры хиазмально-селлярной области. Использование современных методов диагностики и лечения существенно повышает эффективность нейрохирургического вмешательства и снижает риск осложнений у пациентов.

Ключевые слова: аденома гипофиза; эндоскопия; трансфеноидальный подход; соматотропинома; кортикотропинома.

Introduction. Today, surgery has made significant progress in the treatment of pituitary adenomas thanks to the use of endoscopic technologies. This was due to improved visualization of the surgical area due to the introduction of a high-resolution endoscope with wide-screen optics, allowing for a wide-angle image of the area of interest. The use of endoscopes with angled optics (30, 45 and 70 degrees) allowed neurosurgeons to see structures located “around the corner”, which, with a certain tilt of the endoscope, gives almost 180-degree coverage of the area of interest. However, the endoscope itself is only a visualization device, and to carry out the neurosurgical intervention itself, a set of specialized instruments is required.

Surgical technique for treating pituitary adenoma. Surgical treatment of pituitary tumors includes three main stages, or stages: nasal, sphenoidal and sellar. At each stage, the surgeon must go through certain structures using various instruments and equipment. If the bone structures are pronounced and dense, then the surgeon has to use a high-speed bur, which can be used to drill a hole of the required diameter both in the area of the entrance to the main sinus and in the anterior wall of the sella turcica for subsequent surgical removal of the tumor. Upon completion of access to the cavity of the sella turcica, the dura mater (DRM) is dissected and the structure of the pituitary tumor is assessed. For this purpose,

tumor currettes are used, through which the tumor is separated from surrounding structures. If the adenoma has a soft structure, it is removed using tumor cutters and currettes; if the adenoma has a dense structure, it is further peeled off from the surrounding tissues and then removed as a single block or by biting if the size of the adenoma is too large. The “rate of removal” of tumor tissue depends on its consistency. Cystic tumors are removed quickly using an aspirator. Large gelatinous or soft tumors are usually “born” under pressure after dissection of the tumor capsule and are also easily removed with an aspirator and blunt currettes and spoons. In the case of dense and heavy adenomas, severe bleeding of the tumor, the use of sharp currettes and tumor cutters, as well as the second hand of an assistant, may be required to simultaneously grasp the tumor, cut it off from the walls of the sella turcica, as well as simultaneous aspiration of the gushing blood. When installing the endoscope holder, the surgeon has both hands free, which greatly facilitates manipulation in the saddle cavity. However, this is not always convenient, especially when work is carried out using angled optics in the cavity of the cavernous sinus or suprasellar. After removal of the tumor and capsule, the tissue is sent for morphological examination. The stages of tumor tissue removal are as follows: removal begins from the lower part of the tumor, then its lateral parts, and finally the suprasellar component (if any) is removed. When removing the suprasellar part of the tumor, the diaphragm can quickly descend into the sellar cavity and close tumor fragments along the periphery in the formed pockets, especially in the back of the diaphragm. In this situation, it is recommended to regularly monitor the retraction of the diaphragm during the removal of tumor tissue and inspect the formed pockets for the presence of tumor remnants by lifting the dome of the diaphragm with a curved spoon. Extreme care must be taken when removing the lateral portions of the tumor because the medial wall of the cavernous sinus is very thin and can be easily damaged. As mentioned above, the final stage is to remove the suprasellar part of the tumor. In this case, a blunt curette is used, since the arachnoid membrane is often very thin and liquorrhea can develop even with very delicate manipulations. If the diaphragm does not fall evenly, a pocket with remaining tumor may be located behind the descending dome. In this situation, the diaphragm must be gently lifted to visualize the remaining tumor. After the tumor is removed, the lateral and suprasellar regions are examined with 4 mm 30-, 45-, and 70-degree angled endoscopes to identify residual tissue, the presence of liquorrhea, or dural defects. When intraoperative liquorrhea develops, it is desirable to identify the intrasellar defect through which cerebrospinal fluid leaks. Extreme care must be taken not to

make it larger or worsen the situation and, if possible, to stop surgical manipulation around it. Depending on the severity of the defect, it can be sealed with a piece of Tachocomb adhesive plate, autologous fat, muscle or fascia (for example, in cases where the defect was formed as a result of a vertical incision made too high) or autologous tissue can be placed in the saddle cavity and filled with fibrin glue. After this, it is necessary to carry out plastic surgery of the bottom of the sella turcica, if possible suturing the edges of the dura mater with interrupted sutures, or use special clips that avoid the painstaking procedure of tying knots in the depths of the nasal cavity and apply a patch from auto-(fascia, a piece of muscle or fatty tissue) and/or on top or synthetic materials, fastening everything with fibrin glue. After completion of surgical procedures, it is necessary to ensure thorough hemostasis. Minor leakage or bleeding from a branch of the sphenopalatine artery is controlled by bi- or monopolar coagulation. For better healing of the nasal mucosa, it is necessary to ensure that the rostrum of the sphenoid bone is adequately closed with mucosal remnants. A special nasal sponge such as Merocel or Gelfom can be placed on top, which is irrigated with saline solution and removed after 24–48 hours, and the small size of the sponge allows the patient to breathe without experiencing much discomfort. For the first 24 hours, the patient should be in the intensive care unit to stabilize his condition, assess hemodynamics, and identify and manage early postoperative complications. In the first days, it is very important to pay attention to possible manifestations of adrenal insufficiency, as well as the development of diabetes insipidus in order to stop them in a timely manner. To do this, they are guided by both the clinical picture and the data of hormonal studies. so as not to make it larger and not to worsen the situation and, if possible, to stop surgical manipulations around it. Depending on the severity of the defect, it can be sealed with a piece of Tachocomb adhesive plate, autologous fat, muscle or fascia (for example, in cases where the defect was formed as a result of a vertical incision made too high) or autologous tissue can be placed in the saddle cavity and filled with fibrin glue. After this, it is necessary to carry out plastic surgery of the bottom of the sella turcica, if possible suturing the edges of the dura mater with interrupted sutures, or use special clips that avoid the painstaking procedure of tying knots in the depths of the nasal cavity and apply a patch from auto-(fascia, a piece of muscle or fatty tissue) and/or on top or synthetic materials, fastening everything with fibrin glue. After completion of surgical procedures, it is necessary to ensure thorough hemostasis. Minor leakage or bleeding from a

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MRT characteristics of pituitary adenomas. The results of treatment of pituitary adenomas depend not only on correct and timely diagnosis, but also on the nature of tumor growth. One of the leading roles in the diagnosis of pituitary adenomas belongs to radiation research methods - computer (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Due to its high resolution, MRI is the method of choice for detecting pituitary adenomas, especially microadenomas. However, CT also provides significant diagnostic assistance in cases where MRI is impossible (presence of a pacemaker, endoprosthesis), and also helps to better identify bone changes in the nasal cavity, sphenoid sinus, sellar and laterosellar regions. Typically, the normal height of the pituitary gland in adults is no more than 8 mm in men, and no more than 10 mm in women. The adenohipofysis on CT has a homogeneous density, on MRI it has an isointense signal, and in both cases a uniform accumulation of the contrast agent is characteristic. In contrast, the neurohipofysis is characterized by a hyperintense signal on T1-weighted MRI. On MRI, microadenomas in most cases have a hypointense signal in the T1-weighted mode, less often isointense. In the case of microadenomas, a hyperintense T1 signal may indicate hemorrhage into the tumor, which is more typical in prolactinomas. In T2-weighted mode, signal intensity varies and can range from hyperintense to hypointense. When a contrast agent is administered,

it is characterized by a significantly less intense accumulation of it by the tumor compared to normal pituitary tissue. Macroadenomas (tumor size >1 cm) often exhibit extrasellar growth. The tumor can have suprasellar, infrasellar, retrosellar, antesellar, laterosellar growth and their combinations. MRI makes it possible to determine the relationship of the tumor with surrounding structures: optic nerves, chiasm, cavernous sinuses, ICA, floor of the third ventricle, which is important when planning surgical approaches. Most pituitary macroadenomas have a hypointense T1-weighted signal and a hyperintense T2-weighted signal. In addition, they can have both a homogeneous and heterogeneous structure, and also contain a cystic component.

Conclusion. In conclusion, I would like to say that, as a rule, patients easily tolerate endoscopic operations; postoperative complications develop rarely and in a mild form. Of course, this depends on the size of the tumor, the severity of extrasellar growth and the degree of preoperative metabolic disorders. Naturally, the development of more serious complications, both endocrinological and surgical, is possible, including postoperative liquorrhea, bleeding, hematoma formation in the bed of the removed tumor, and even death.

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